

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE OFFICIAL BUSINESS STYLE IN MODERN ENGLISH**Rajabova S.**

*Doctor of Philosophy in Germanic
Azerbaijan University of Languages,
Department of Foreign Languages in Education
Baku, Azerbaijan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17583051>*

Abstract

This paper presents characteristics of the official business style in modern English. In connection with the great changes taking place in the economy of our country in the modern era and the process of integration into the world market where international communication is conducted in English, there is a necessary need to train specialist personnel who have mastered business English at a high level.

The official business style is a functional style of the modern English literary language that is used to create various documents, legal acts, and in official communication between citizens, organizations, and social groups. The official business style is characterized by the presence of special business standards that are used to create documents such as applications, business letters, protocols, reports, certificates, powers of attorney, contracts, and more. The official-business style of speech performs informative and persuasive functions, which consist of reporting on the state of affairs, stating facts, or giving instructions for performing certain actions.

Keywords: *integration, international standards, pragmatic parameters, colloquial nature, official-business*

Introduction

English is recognized as the language of international communication not only in the business and economic spheres, but also in its various fields of application, for example, in international negotiations, air and sea navigation, customs clearance, etc., this sphere is also distinguished by its noticeable specialization at different levels of the language hierarchy. In most countries of the world where English is not a native language, people actively use it in their daily professional activities. Due to the continuous expansion of the Foreign-Economic Relations of our country, the increasing number of people involved in the sphere of entrepreneurial activity, the introduction of international standards, especially norms and rules of the official-business English language into the world languages is taking place [1, p.121].

In recent years, the official-business English language has attracted the attention of many specialists, leading to the compilation of dictionaries, reference books, and the preparation of text samples. In modern conditions, at a time when the real functionality of the language system is involved in the analysis, taking into account the “communication factor”, such studies are considered relevant in which language phenomena, including texts, are studied by taking into account functional and pragmatic parameters [2, p.263]

In the Anglo-Saxon period, the official-business style of the English language was mainly realized in oral speech. In the XI-XIV centuries – during the Middle English period, thousands of words from Latin and Greek enter the English language, both from French and through the French language. In the XV-XVI centuries, legislative acts begin to take on their modern form, the number of genres increases, the rules for their compilation appear. The formation and development of the official-business style falls on the middle and New periods of the English language. In the Middle English period, business documentation increases the number of genres, and in the new English period, the rules for their compilation appear.

In the era of Old English, there were only separate genres of business documents: law, charter, will. During the period of Middle English, when Britain came to the rule of the Normans (XI-XIV centuries), thousands of words from Latin and Greek enter English, both from French and through French: *attaché*, *embargo*, *courtoisie*, *detente*, *nuncio*, *ukase*. At the same time, this area is expanding with the internal means of the English language. e. g. : *citizen*, *citizenship*, *client state*, *pol*, *resident* etc. [10, p.52]

Among the bookish styles of the English language, the official-business style (also known as the clerical style) is the most boring. Its language is composed of speech idioms (*clichés*), bureaucratic terms, and a clear syntactic structure. However, it is the official-business style that people encounter on a daily basis. This is the style of announcements, certificates, protocols, reports, and various documents. The style of these papers simplifies formal communication by providing uniformity and limiting the content of business documents to only necessary information, allowing for a concise presentation.

The study of the official-business style seems to us important and promising, since its sphere of service is the most important aspects of state life. In this regard, the current study can be considered as an attempt to consider official-business English as a functional variant of this language within the system, as a social phenomenon determined by the use of linguistic means in a specific communicative situation. The analysis focuses on specific lexicons, morphological means and syntactic constructions used in texts of official-business style, terms, stable and unstable combinations, standards and labels of official-business nature. All these aspects of the official-business style of the English language are relevant due to the fact that they have not been touched upon in the studies so far and for the reasons listed above.

The official-business style in English is a functional style used in the sphere of official and business

relations to convey accurate, unambiguous, and standard information in documents such as laws, contracts, official letters, instructions, and references. It is characterized by an impersonal nature, the absence of expression and evaluation, and the use of special vocabulary, bookish words, and fixed phrases, which ensures a standardized and complete presentation of facts.

The task of this style is to convey information and give instructions. The official-business style is characterized by precision, unambiguity, impersonal nature, standardized construction of the text, and the imperative nature of the text.

Official business style is a functional style of the English language that is used in the sphere of official and business relations, in particular, in administrative and legal activities. It is used in legislative acts, contracts, business correspondence, applications and other

documents. Official business style is one of the book styles, used in the sphere of business relations, business papers, laws, documents, acts, contracts, regulations, charters, official correspondence, etc. [7, p.5].

The official-business style lacks emotionally colored and foreign-style, colloquial vocabulary, since documents compiled in accordance with the requirements of this style are practically devoid of expressivity, they do not use visual and expressive means of language. On the contrary, in business texts there is a mandatory prescriptive stylistic coloring, which is achieved through the use of adverbs (for example: one must strictly observe ..., one must resolutely eliminate ...) and verbs in the infinitive with the imperative mood (for example: determine the list of necessary measures ..., establish the location... correct the existing shortcomings..., it is necessary to allow...).

Materials and methods.

The purpose of this style is to convey information, give instructions. The official business style is characterized by precision, unambiguity, impersonal character, standardized text structure, and the obligatory-prescriptive nature of the text.

Official business style is a type of literary language that serves the sphere of official business relations: relations between government authorities and the population, between countries, between enterprises, organizations, institutions, between the individual and society [9, p.252].

The business style is characterized by a distinctive vocabulary and phraseology with a pronounced functional and stylistic coloring that is not found in other styles.

The content and style of a text are largely determined by the type of document, and each genre has its own specialized means of expression. However, despite the diversity of genres, the business style is characterized by a certain stability in the organization and composition of language resources.

Characteristic features of the official business style:

- functioning mainly in written form (rarely encountered in oral speech: in the form of a report before a meeting, in the form of business negotiations, an oral diplomatic statement);

- use for the transmission of highly specialized information (legal or diplomatic);

- stability, tradition, uniformity;

- conciseness and compactness of presentation; accuracy and completeness of formulations;

- impeccability in legal terms;

- standard language when presenting typical situations of business communication;

- neutral tone of presentation;

- compliance with the norms of official etiquette, which is manifested in the choice of stable forms of address and words and phrases corresponding to the genre, in construction of a phrase and the entire text;

- the absence of manifestation of the author's speech individuality, which is allowed only in certain types of business letters, in diplomatic correspondence, in oral negotiations [6, p.658]

The function of business style is that it gives the presentation the character of a document and thereby

transfers the various aspects of human relations reflected in this document into the category of official business.

The business sphere is represented by international relations, jurisprudence, economics, military industry, advertising, communication in official institutions, government activities. Official business style is the language of documents, official papers and business meetings.

Each style is a relatively stable system at the present stage of the development of the literary language. Therefore, the style of the language is a historical category. Semantic structure of the early Anglo-Saxon code of law; structural-semantic features of the laws of the Kings of Kent and Wessex; architectonics of the Old English code of law; a number of categories of the text of the ancient law (temporality, locality, personality, modality, etc.) Y.A. Kolyadin is widely interpreted in the scientific work [8, p.24].

A.A. Putin notes that neutral, poetic, official-business and scientific styles already existed in the stylistic layers of Old English, and also emphasizes that at that time words and phrases of a colloquial nature were not used in texts at all [10, p.53].

T.V. Uskova in her research shows that a number of legal terms used in modern English are reflected in written monuments dating back to the seventh century: "bequlath, goods, guilt, land, manslaughter, murder, theft, sheriff, steal, thief, ward, guardianship, swear" [11, p.12].

In order to determine the history of the official-business style of the English language, M. Malovichko compares existing genres with those that came to them in ancient times. For example, in modern times, existing legislative acts (legal type of business documents), texts of statutes (socio-political and industrial spheres) and texts of contracts (economic relations) correspond to the laws of legislators that existed in early times, on the other hand, guilds comply with the statutes and orders of the charters [9, p.61].

Functional styles continue to develop in the middle and new English era as well. In the Middle English period, new genres appear that serve the business sphere, while in the new English period their number multiplies (the influence of Norman culture led to the differentiation of genres, to an increase in their number). In the Middle English period, precision and clarity are observed in the expression of the business style. In the New English period, macrostructural features - narrative linguistic features are formed. The texts of business documents are conservative and are still prone to stereotyping [9, p.144].

The formation and development of the official-business style falls on the middle and New periods of the English language. In the Middle English period, business documentation increases the number of genres, and in the new English period, the rules for their compilation appear. If in the Middle and New English periods the charter was drawn up according to the model of law, then in a certain short time the charters began to be drawn up according to the charter. [10, p.56].

At the new English stage, the main features of the style are formed: generalization of information and at

the same time its excess, nominativeness, maximum expression of logical relations between phenomena, which led to the predominance of subordinate compound sentences in the syntax [5, p.145].

Intra-textual changes in the new English period are both sociological (as a result of cultural development) and linguistic (thus, the development of a system of conjunctions in the middle and new English periods affects the formation of their exponential plan). In all texts of the charter characteristic of the XV-XVIII centuries, multi-component constructions are used, which have a relationship of both subordination and non-subordination. Later, such phenomena are entrenched in the texts of legality, which require an accurate and logical expression of the content, and characterize them [5, p.179].

Of course, if the official-business style of the English language has passed a long way of development, it is still in development. This is also conditioned by both linguistic and extra linguistic factors. The linguistic factor is that the language is in constant development, without this development the language will go out of use, and since the extra linguistic factor is associated with society, the changes taking place here must necessarily be reflected in the language.

Extra linguistic (socio-psychological) factors of communication conditions have a great influence on the formation of the official-business style, as a result of which acquisitions and expressive-emotional units were formed in these semi-styles [2, p.264].

The features of the official business style are predetermined by extra linguistic (external to the language) factors. Let's list these factors:

1. The most basic extra linguistic factor is the purpose of communication. The regulatory function of the official-business style is the main function. Moreover, the main purpose of such communication is to achieve an agreement between the two contracting parties.

2. Stylistic features depend on the structural-compositional decomposition of the text.

3. Imperative form, imperativeness (приказ). This feature is manifested in the regular use of infinitives, in the use of tense forms in the sense of indication; in the use of words expressing will (*allow, prohibited, necessary, allowed*), passive constructions (certificates are issued on request). These signs can be seen in the job descriptions.

4. Accuracy that does not allow for other interpretations. A double interpretation loses the authority of the document.

5. Standardization arising from the regulatory and regulatory function of documentation. This feature is reflected in the use of fixed expressions (*in accordance with the procedure established by law, after the expiration of the term*). The following continuous sentence expressions are used in the texts of documents: *at the end, upon arrival, signed and sealed, to the address*. Templates and standards are a characteristic feature of the style of official documents, since the subject area of business speech is strictly defined, the cases of its application are relatively few and identical. Template expressions are important for creating the layout of the document. Each official document has a certain compositional structure: memoranda, contracts, business

letters, etc. - in all these cases, the structure of the text is related to the direct content of the text and carries a semantic load.

6. Objectivity. This feature is expressed in the impersonality of the interpretation, the rare occurrence of the first and second person in the use of pronouns and verb forms, the high frequency of third person forms, the use of passive constructions: *a pension is assigned, a scholarship is awarded*.

7. Brevity, achieved through the economical and efficient use of language tools. Brevity is the main feature of the language of business communication. This is explained by the need for quick perception of information. In a business letter, it is important to find a balance between brevity and completeness of information. The brevity of the information expressed necessitates the use of a large number of abbreviations and various types of abbreviations [2, p.262].

Discussion

In the history of the study of the styles of the English language, first of all an important role was played by I.R. Galperin's works on Stylistics, which can be considered reliable sources. I.R. Galperin distinguishes five styles in modern English: artistic, journalistic, functional style of newspaper, scientific and official documents. He did not include the style of speech in the classification of styles. He had a new idea of also lies in the fact that he divides texts belonging to a certain style into genres.

For example, military texts belonging to the official style include orders, Information, Regulations (rules), instructions; while diplomatic texts include notes, declarations, agreements, etc. covers. In the formal-business style, the rules are more observed, the degree of regulation is higher in the formal style than in the scientific or journalistic style. After reviewing the classifications, we can draw some results. No classification can be complete, universal, useful (suitable). But each classification reflects common features and differences [3, p.91].

Structural, stylistic and pragmatic features of English-language military discourse by T.S. Yusupova, the use of English military discourse units in the media, the classification of military lexicon, the metaphor of lexicon, etc. issues have been investigated [12, p.18].

The ideas of English stylists about the official-business style are distinguished by their diversity. So, well-known specialists in the field of stylistics of the English language D. Crystal and D. Davis identify five "basic linguistic forms" that correspond to the system of functional styles: "the spoken language, the language of written documents, the religious language, the language of newspapers, and the language of legislative acts" [2, p.264]. D. Crystal and D. Davis concludes that within styles, only any linguistic phenomena, units, can be processed in an artistic style; while in the remaining "languages" (styles), they are referred to as "limited" languages, since some forms of language are processed. English stylists also note that the use of certain language units and forms depends on one or another circumstance.

The study of the official-business style of the English language is applied, as the English-language literature mainly deals with the relationship of Business English with teaching methods [6, p.658].

"He headed the London Center for the study of Contemporary English language usage (the Survey of English Usage) R. Quirk has developed a classification of registers" [2, p.131].

Linguists of the center of London divide all styles into two large groups: spoken and written styles, which are divided into smaller semi-classes. So, the style of speech includes:

1. "Conversation (for example, a conversation on the phone; ordinary conversation – a conversation that is observed with the permission of the interviewees and observed without their knowledge). This half-style, on the other hand, consists of: a familial style (i.e. suggestibility), which indicates that the interlocutors are in close relationship; a style of equality, which indicates that the social positions (strata's) of the interlocutors in society are equal; and, conversely, a style that indicates inequality."

2. "Outside, spontaneous comments (sports and non-sports comments)";

3. "Speech, prepared without prior preparation";

4. "Pre-prepared speech".

According to R. Quirk's classification, the genres of the official-business style we studied were attributed to different groups of this classification [3, p.133]. For example, while technical texts are not taken into account in the classification, humanitarian texts are recorded; or the distinction between pre-prepared speeches and pre-written official news and newspaper texts is not clearly traced.

The number of genres of the official-business style is large, the genres themselves are diverse, and this diversity also makes it difficult to systematize and analyze genres. It should be noted that the common feature of semi-styles is the presence of stamps. It is impossible to imagine an application, diploma, passport or any other official document in the right to leave. But each genre has its own rules of compilation.

Speaking about the general issues of speech styles and genre/style classification, notes that "due to the rapid development of social stylesheet factors. Stylistics is the consideration of an increasing number of exact manifestations of the functional - stylistic uniqueness of communication. In general, it is necessary to pay special attention to the interaction of fully defined functions and stylesheet factors" [3, p.133].

Function of style-an abstract category that expresses the generalized purpose of a particular field of communication. It is also sometimes called the pragmatics of style.

The term "functional style" reflects the specific functions of the language, depending on the type of interaction of communication.

The main purpose or function of the formal-business style - is to interpret the conditions binding on the two parties and to achieve an agreement between the two contracting parties.

The public function of written business speech is very important and peculiar: business serves public re-

lations between people, coordination of the work of departments, speech organizations and the activities of the population.

The regulatory function of the official-business style is indicated as the main function, i.e., it involves the establishment of norms and rules in the field of Public Relations (for example, relations of individuals, relations between groups and individuals, relations of social groups and institutions, etc.) reflect. The main goal of such communication is to express the conditions that unite the two parties in the obligation.

In other words, the purpose of communication in this style is to achieve an agreement between the two contracting parties.

The language means of the official-business style can be characterized as follows: 1) lexicon and phraseology with the corresponding functional-stylistic overtones; 2) language means used in neutral and book Language; 3) language means neutral in stylistic overtones, but acting as a sign of a certain semi-style in terms of frequency of use.

According to a number of foreign scientists, radical changes in the business style are taking place. For example E. Gowers believes that in the business sphere of the official-business style in English, a large number of meaningless administrative and clerical formulas (expressions) are superfluous [4, p.272]. This idea was expressed by E. Partridge also supports. [5, p.380] L. Alexander generally denies the existence of the English business language and demands simplicity and clarity [1, p.121]. Of course, we cannot agree with the idea of denying the existence of the English business language.

Among the functional styles of the literary language, the official-business style is of great importance. Official-business style is the language of laws and official documents by which socio-legal relations are regulated.

"Documentation covers the diplomatic, legislative, managerial, economic, political and social activities of the state. Intergovernmental and intra-state relations are formalized and regulated by documents. In addition to having valuable legal content, the documents are also of historical importance" [16, p.173].

Document-is a text that controls the actions of people and has legal significance. It is for this reason that the text of the document makes high demands on the accuracy of meaning and content, which does not capture non-narrative (ambiguity) in the eye. Only pre-prepared and edited written speech meets these requirements. It is impossible to achieve this degree of accuracy, since oral speech is not pre-prepared, self-formed and variative. In addition to denotative accuracy (literally meaning) to the language of documents, the requirement of communicative accuracy is also put forward – an adequate reflection of reality, author's opinion in a piece of speech (sentence, text) [9, p.225].

Since the twentieth century, the process of unification in documentation has become more widespread. The emergence of unified forms for writing business letters in service-specific documents has led to the development of new standards of business letter and stencil texts. In the era of computerization, this is more sig-

nificant. Fixed formulas, accepted abbreviations, uniform sequence of information on these forms, as a rule, ease the encoding of information and save time.

The language of official-business documents, on the one hand, is close to the scientific style, since there is a change in the knowledge of the addressee as a communicative result of both styles; on the other hand, it is close to the journalistic style, since the result of the influence of texts of both styles is manifested in the activity of the addressee [16, p.175].

"In scientific prose, as well as in journalistic and political discourses, the prospects for the prevalence of figurative – associative price sets within different compositional-speech forms, the study of the degrees and limits of predictability, incompleteness of provisions, proposals are of particular relevance" [13, p.592].

According to I. R. Galperin, "the language of official-business documents uses expressions from the early Victorian era. The vocabulary of these documents is conservative, that is, legislative documents retain most of the formal and archaic words used in their lexicographic meaning [3, p.332].

The official-business style, as is known, does not accept words with an emotional tinge, connotative words, and therefore we note a sign of non-emotionality of the style. This feature applies to both the written and oral form of the style. However, there is a tendency to this in diplomatic or in some economic documents (informative genre), in business correspondence ("business style"). Metaphors and comparisons, which are used here in a limited number, act as a means of simple expressiveness, they are more clarifying than figurative.

-The official business style is characterized by the use of the following linguistic means:

- at the level of vocabulary: the use of full names and exact dates;
- bookish vocabulary (due to, during, because of, characterized by);
- the use of words in their direct meanings;
- the absence of expressive and evaluative vocabulary;
- the frequent use of verbal nouns (approval, use, implementation);
- the presence of standardized phrases (after the expiration of the term, in accordance with the established procedure, to enter into force);
- limited possibilities for synonymous substitution, frequent lexical repetitions.

"The title words, which are considered special lexicons, indicate that they are far from connotative, but are used in a denotative sense and have an emotional tinge only in this genre. In other styles, such words are used in a neutral style". Vocabulary with an emotional tinge is used in business letters in phrases of appeal, in parts of request, refusal, and conclusion.

When describing the property of accuracy, I. Galperin writes: "each official document has its own unique composition. Pacts, charters, orders and meeting proto-branches, codices and memoranda have one or another certain external form" [3, p.328]. So, the feature of accuracy presupposes the structure, compilation of an official document. Moreover, ambiguity in the

language of official documents is not allowed, as it can lead to a dual understanding of what is written.

The indicated stylistic features, in connection with each other, create a formal-business functional style system. These stylistic features, manifested in English-language official-business documents, play a huge role in creating a lexical, morphological and syntactic structure.

We have already mentioned, the establishment of legal states and the laws of a market economy put forward a number of requirements for the modern field of business. These requirements are met through properly drawn up documents. Therefore, it is necessary to study the theoretical foundations for working with these documents.

Many types of business documents have a generally accepted form of presentation and arrangement of material, which undoubtedly makes them easier and more convenient to use. It is no coincidence that in certain cases of business practice, ready-made forms are used that only need to be filled out. Even envelopes are customarily addressed in a specific order (varying from country to country, but firmly established in each of them), which has its advantages for both writers and postal workers. Therefore, all the speech clichés that simplify and speed up business communication are quite appropriate.

Business documents have a number of linguistic features, which must meet the following requirements:

1) socio-cultural requirements for mutual understanding of the author and the party receiving the document, in other words, communicative, communication purpose;

2) certain stylistic norms;

3) pragmatic requirements of the text (accuracy and effectiveness of content);

4) lexical-semantic requirements;

5) logical and syntactic requirements [16, p.180];

When choosing and processing morphemes, word forms, word combinations, sentences and paragraph in business documents, the main attention is paid to the fact that they meet the norms of the official-business style of the English language.

What specific form of manifestation of language we use determines communication that takes place in certain social conditions. Functional Stylistics studies socially conditioned types of language.

The term "functional style" reflects the specific functions of language depending on the type of interaction of communication. When it comes to the classification of styles and the characteristics of styles, I. R. Galperin focuses more on the use of various lexical and grammatical means, on the feature of style development in a certain field of communication, that is, its functionality. He studies language functions, offers a description of functional styles based on a combination of stylistic functions. The official-business style that interests us here, according to I. V. Arnold, performs 2 functions: an intellectual communicative function and a pragmatic function [17, p. 26]. The main purpose or function of the official-business style is to interpret the terms that are binding on both parties and to achieve agreement between the two parties who have come to an agreement.

Each substyle can be expressed in written and oral form. Official business documents exist mainly in a regulated written form and regulate the legal and business relations of individuals and legal entities. The oral form of official business speech - speeches at ceremonial meetings, banquets, reports of state and public figures, etc. is reflected.

Thus, the regulatory function of the official-business style is indicated as the main function, that is, it reflects the establishment of norms and rules in the field of public relations (for example, relations between individuals, relations between groups and individuals, relations between social groups and institutions, etc.). The main purpose of such communication is to express the conditions that bind the two parties to the obligation. In other words, the purpose of communication in this style is to achieve agreement between the two parties who have come to an agreement [17, p.85].

Functional style is a system of interconnected language tools that serve a specific purpose in communication. It is not the linguistic means or stylistic techniques themselves, but precisely the interaction of linguistic means and stylistic techniques that make up the distinctive features of each style. Styles differ not only in lexical and grammatical features, but also in the frequency of use of the indicated linguistic units [3, p.332].

In the interrogative dictionary of linguistic terms, style is defined as follows: "Style – 1. The type of language characterized in terms of the choice of language means in relation to the purpose of communication, the ability to coordinate and combine selective units. Language style. Functional style.

2. The sum of the methods of using language tools typical for the author, work, genre. Fuzuli style. Classic style. Drama style. Satire style.

3. The use of language tools according to their expressive shade on the principle of selection and substitution. Book style. Satirical style.

4. Writing or speaking on the basis of the syntactic rules of the language and the norms of vocabulary. Artificial style. Sloppy styling. Wrong style". "Language style-a style taken as one of the semi systems belonging to the language system [17, p.84].

The realization of such a semi system is considered a speech style. All styles grouped according to the functional and expressive principle are considered linguistic styles. ... Official-administrative style is a style used in business correspondence, official documents, papers belonging to departments, which is usually characterized by the use of archaic structure and words, word combinations.

Functional styles-styles that are distinguished based on the main functions of the language (communication, information and influence). There are the following types: scientific style (information function), artistic style (influence function), press style (influence function), everyday-household style (communication function), official-administrative style (communication function)" "Official style is a style of inherent mainly in the language of state documents, which is characterized by its accuracy". "Business style is a branch of the official literary language in which there is no or very

little emotionality, as well as stamps typical of the stationery style are not used" [17, p.84].

In addition, we must add that this style not only performs communication, but also the function of informing, ordering and asking. Thus, the style of language can be defined as a system of language means intended for the performance of a certain communicative function and directed to a certain effect, or as interconnected and mutually conditioned language means.

The difference between styles with a functional character is related to the word treasury of the language. Because the language first of all manifests its strength of expression in the lexical means of the language with stylistic nuances. However, the selection of grammatical forms, syntactic compositions and their use each time correspond to the requirements and goals of the functional style.

"However, it should be noted that each of the functional styles creates a complex system. Functional styles are divided into different types of speech. It works through such speech activities. In the process, it is formed, developed and improved. For example, this process is carried out through political-diplomatic, socio-political, socio-legal conversations in the official-business style" [14, p.136].

According to S.Fataliyeva's idea, such terms as "functional style of language" and "functional style of speech" have the same essence [17, p. 83]. However, we cannot agree with this opinion, because in this case we would equate language and speech.

T. Afandiyeva rightly writes about this: "in linguistic Stylistics, the styles of the literary language are named through various terms: language styles, speech styles, functional styles.

Language is a system. It is a system of sounds, signs, images, words. It is speech that initiates this system and makes it operational. Language is a category in a relatively static state, and speech is its dynamics, movement and creation. And during this movement, speech contributes to the development of language, serves for its decomposition into styles. Style, like a fragment of the literary language, develops thanks to speech. Because style, as part of the language, which is a "system of systems", is also a system: it is a system consisting of a variety of types of genres. Therefore, the process of decomposition of the style continues inside: the style is divided into separate types of speech, serving different types of genres. For example, the official-business style includes stationery, acts, protocols, applications, diplomatic correspondence, speeches of lawyers, various legal papers and documents, etc. it's about genres. And each style, which consists of the corresponding types of speech, performs its social function thanks to these types of speech. Therefore, it is more expedient to use the term functional style" [15, p.184].

"By the norm of style we mean the specific norms and characteristics of each style. Normativity manifests itself differently in different functional styles. For example, building a statement in a formal business style necessarily requires compliance with all style rules. However, in scientific stylistic texts, the addition of non-stylistic overtones is allowed. This is done in order to emphasize and distinguish the individual authorship of the researcher" [14, p.136].

The term "norm" used by E. Coseriu corresponds to the term "functional style". In his opinion, the norm – not what can be said, but what has already been said, and what is said according to tradition in society corresponds to it. The system covers the ideal forms of certain linguistic realization, i.e. the method (technique) and the standards for the corresponding linguistic activity; the norm, on the other hand, concentrates the models that have already been realized historically by means of this method and have been realized on these benchmarks.

"The system is a system of possibilities, a system of encounters, and the norm is a system of forced realizations. A system is ideal forms of certain linguistic realizations, and the norm is a model, a historically technically realized template. The norm is synchronous, it is the external and internal balance of the system. Speakers do not perceive the norm of the language they speak, or it is in the subconscious layer, because this hour attracts attention when foreigners do not follow the norm. But all language carriers are well aware of this" [17, p.5].

There is also a special list of anthroponomy that refer to people with certain professions and specialties and the duties they perform, which is a business norm of the English language: "teller", "auditor", "accountant", "manager", "executor", "testator", "vendor", "purchaser". "In other (non-business) areas of the language, words with such lexical-semantic meaning are not used in the same way". "At the syntactic level, it is possible to observe the development of parallel structures, explanatory-defining branched sentences, sentence models corresponding to the scientific style. texts written in the official-business style are not intended simply for reading. They are intended for correct, accurate analysis and study in a calm, relaxed environment. Therefore, they are distinguished by the fact that they contain a large number of long sentences" [16, p.104].

Norm-uses only part of the options offered by the system. In the same order, the functional style uses all the variety of linguistic material only its individual units and constructions. For each functional style, a set of frequently used typical forms is typical. E. Coseriu writes: "the norm includes existing elements manifested from its traditional point of view, whereas the language system is an open system that includes those that have not yet been realized in the virtual, but which may be possible in its processing on the basis of its distinctive encounters and rules of association " [14, p.136].

He reveals the functional style as follows: "functional styles are subsystems of language, each of which has its own specific features, which are found in lexicon, phraseology, syntactic units, and sometimes in phonetics. The formation and existence of functional styles is conditioned by the uniqueness of communication conditions in various fields of human activity."

S. Fataliyeva gives a clear and clear definition of the official-business style: "the task of the official-business style is related to the texts in which state and Public Administration documents are written. One of the main features of the official-business style is that it has a specific lexicon. So, in this style, explanation and descriptive means are no longer allowed to explain some

issue. This style has its own peculiarities. Order, decision, contract, decree, law, resolution, charter, statement, ultimatum, etc. in official documents such as, the idea is concrete, consistent, clear and convincing.

In the official-business style, standard phrases and ready-made expressions are used, artistic means of description are not used. In the official-business style, field terms, nationwide words are used, depending on the type of document [17, p.84].

"The use of official lexical units in other styles is conditional. These lexical units in many cases lose their formality.

Official-business style in its oral form must strictly adhere to the orthoepic norms of the literary language. In this case, the use of phonetic dialethism is a violation of the norm.

It is also important that lexical norms are observed in the official-business style. So, in this style, it is strictly forbidden to use

During the investigation, it turns out that violations of the spelling rules in the language of official documents cannot be allowed at all. Because important official and state documents have a certain functional essence of secrecy and absolutism" [14, p.116].

The verbal form of the official-business style should also be used less often than polysyllabic compound words. The overload of the official-business style with such words, which is already considered a heavy style in its character, leads to the disappearance of a number of its specific features (fast-and clear speech, providing a lot and comprehensive information in little time)" [7, p.19].

The main features of this style are: precision, impersonal character, stereotypical text structure, prescriptive character. Scope of application: laws, by-laws, orders, regulations, certificates, instructions, announcements, business letters, reports, memos, etc.

The official business style is a type of literary language that serves the sphere of official business relations: relations between government authorities and the population, between countries, between enterprises, organizations, institutions, between the individual and society.

The official-business style is a functional style of speech, a means of written communication in the field of business relations: in the field of legal relations and management. This area covers international relations, the economy, the military industry, the field of advertising, communication in official institutions, and government activities. Sub-styles: legislative (used in the field of state administration, the volitional nature of the function is manifested); administrative-chancellery (conducting personal business papers, institution documents, emphasizes the nature of administrative relations - loans, advances); diplomatic sub-style (at the international level, relations between the government and diplomats) [1, p.121].

The official business style is the style of documents: international treaties, state acts, legal laws, regulations, statutes, instructions, official correspondence, business papers, etc. Despite the differences in content and the variety of genres, the official business style is generally characterized by a number of common features. These include:

1) conciseness, compactness of presentation, and economical use of language resources;

2) standard arrangement of the material, the frequent requirement for a form (identity card, various kinds of diplomas, birth and marriage certificates, money documents, etc.), the use of terms characteristic of this style

3) extensive use of terminology, names (legal, diplomatic, military, administrative, etc.), the presence of a special vocabulary and phraseology (official, clerical), the inclusion of abbreviated words and acronyms in the text;

4) narrative nature of the presentation, the use of nominative sentences with enumeration;

5) the direct order of words in a sentence as the predominant principle of its construction;

6) the tendency to use complex sentences that reflect the logical subordination of one fact to another;

7) the almost complete absence of emotionally expressive speech devices and established expressions;

8) the weak individualization of style.

Official business style serves: a) the sphere of business relations, b) the area of law; c) the area of interstate politics. This is the most ancient of the book styles.

Among the bookish styles of the English language, the official-business style stands out for its relative stability and closed nature. Over time, it naturally undergoes some changes due to the nature of the content itself, but many of its features, historically established genres, specific vocabulary, phraseology, and syntactic patterns, give it a generally conservative character. Many types of business documents have established forms of presentation and organization, which makes them easier to use. Often, ready-made forms are used, which only need to be filled out. For example, it is customary to write envelopes in a certain order, different in different countries, but firmly established in each of them - it is convenient for both writers and postal workers. Therefore, speech clichés that simplify and speed up business communication are quite appropriate in it [2, p.264].

The main functions of the official business style: communicating information and influencing the addressee. Hence the main modes of speech: stating (communicating about something existing) and imperative (commanding). The main genres: international treaties, government acts, legal laws, decrees, orders, charters, instructions, official correspondence, business papers (certificates, certificates, powers of attorney, applications, etc.). All genres of the official business style are different documents.

The official business style has a dual nature: on the one hand, it expresses specific content (and is close to the scientific style), on the other hand, it is in contact with everyday life (for example, in the sphere of administrative and economic activity) and must be understandable to any person (unlike the scientific style). This duality determined the following main features of the official business style: precision of wording, which does not allow for the possibility of another interpretation; clarity and detail of presentation (especially in laws, instructions, etc.); laconicism (brevity) of the

text, which is achieved by the economical use of linguistic means, excluding verbosity; standard presentation (achieved by the use of stable formulas of business language); standard text design (determined by the current GOST); neutral tone of presentation (emotionally colored and expressive vocabulary is excluded). ODS functions mainly in written form, but its oral form is not excluded: speeches of state and public figures at meetings, receptions, ceremonial meetings, business negotiations, oral orders, etc. [11, p.25].

It is known that the vocabulary of the language is divided into two large groups: the general and the group used in the field of destruction. Since the common words of the vocabulary form the basis of the lexicon of the language, they are used in all styles and areas: political, economic, cultural, domestic, etc. Therefore, various thematic groups are distinguished within the generally changing words. There are no restrictions on the processing of these.

"Lexicon belonging to a limited circle of use is used within a certain space, or in a circle of people united by a profession, a social trait, a common interest" [2, p.264].

Terms also refer to the limited scope of use. Terms are units of a particular branch of science. The term (lat. terminus-limit, limit) is a word or combination of words that accurately and unambiguously names a certain concept belonging to a particular field and states its connection with other concepts. According to the calculations of scientists, the share of terminological lexicon in texts of this style can reach up to 25%.

"Unlike terms, that is, the official scientific names of special concepts, art-professional units act in oral speech as 'semi-official' words that do not carry strict scientific prostration". However, terms, art-professional units and international abbreviations are closely related.

Three layers are distinguished in the lexicon of business documents: scientific and technical lexicon; special lexicon (terms) and general lexicon. The main goal of developing a special lexicon is to create aspects of formality, clarity and non-emotionality in documents related to the business style.

Along with official terms, the official style of the English language also uses professional words, barbarism and units belonging to colloquial discourse. This also proves that official language is to some extent emotional-expressive. Professional words related to the military lexicon: tin fish (literal: tin fish) - submarine; tin-hat (literal: tin hat) - steel helmet; piper (military trumpeter); outer (knock out with a blow) [9, p.252].

Unlike borrowed words, barbarisms are not assimilated in the language and retain their own external form. The words and phrases from Latin and French are mainly used in barbarisms. Barbarisms are divided into two groups:

1. Those that are used as synonyms of real English terms. For example, in the field of law: habeas corpus (lat.)- a court order to transfer a prisoner to ruin in order to check the legality of the arrest, to check the legality of the charge; crime false (lat.) - fraud; corpus juris (lat.) - code of law/charter, quorum (lat.) - quorum; status quo (lat.).

2. Auxiliary phrases used in speech. For example, clarifying, complementing the idea that is regularly processed and expressed in legal discourse: prima facie (lat.)- at first glance; in toto (lat.)- whole; bona fide (lat.)- conscience/ sincere, (a bona fide confession-sincere confession); par excellence (fren.)- most often, mainly, pro tempore (lat.)- temporary; condition sine qua non (lat.)- absolute condition; mutatis mutandis (lat.)- with appropriate /desired modifications.

Professional words used in the field of Law: Civil and Political Rights; Commission on Human Rights; Freedom of opinion and expression; Freedom of religion; Freedom of peaceful assembly and association.

In the field of law, separate colloquial words can act as terms or professional words: slander finding - court order, begging, four corners - the legal meaning of which is the full text of the document and the whole (not in parts) value, forum shopping - the search for judges by the parties in the event (it is believed that this may lead to a favorable outcome), gentlemen's agreement - is an unwritten agreement that cannot be enforced by law, but is supported by the conscience of the parties, heir / collateral heir / lineal heir - heir/indirect heir/first degree heir, hornbook - a textbook that is considered authoritative in the field of law and is often cited in it lame duck - an unelected official man, law of the land - laws operating in a specific country, loan-sharking - illegal business of lending money at interest; magistrate-having limited jurisdiction or responsibility judicial officer; used in colloquial speech as a synonym for the word judge; on all fours - a legal precedent or event, the exact nature of the case under consideration; squandering (in the military field: waste) [11, p.25].

In the official-business style, the lexical norms of the literary language are strictly observed: the text does not include informal, dialect and slang lexicon.

We correctly note that some of the linguistic units act as terms in the functional aspect; and in the structural aspect - as idioms. Therefore, the boundary between the term and the idiom is uncertain. In the examples presented below, the terms idiom is characteristic, and this characteristic serves to perform a number of communicative functions.

Idioms are divided into 4 groups according to the denotative functions they perform:

1) idioms used in a narrow sense. *Pardon*-forgiveness, as a form of forgiveness; hard labor (literally-hard labor) as a form of hard work, hard work in the true sense;

2) idioms used in a broad sense. The true meaning of these idioms is broader in volume than the initial literal meaning. For example: kidnapping (kid "child" + nab/nap "steal") - literally means "child abduction", but its real meaning denotes the abduction of people of any age: "kidnapping. The felony of abducting an individual by force". And this meaning is much broader than the original meaning. Also: housebreaking (literally - storming a dwelling) in the real sense - illegal entry into any premises (that is, not only a dwelling).

3) idioms whose meanings have partially changed. For example, manslaughter (literally - massacre) legal meaning - not intentional homicide.

4) idioms used figuratively. This includes all types of metaphor and metonymy. For example: to churn - the

original meaning is “to shake the oil”; and the legal meaning is the investment of money in other purposes, the legal meaning of four corners (four corners) – the value of the document as a whole (not in parts) [7, p.19]

In the official-business style, phraseologisms with a neutral character are used: be significant (to matter), be of importance (to play a role), occupy a post (to occupy a position), sphere of application (area of use), to cause damage, whereabouts (place), etc.

There are clichés and phrases that can easily introduce a formal-business style, for example: “I beg to inform you, the above-mentioned, hereinafter named, on behalf of, private advisory, Dear Sir, your obedient servants, to constitute a basis; to draw consequences”.

In fact, each half-style also has its own special terms and expressions, which differ from the corresponding expressions of other half-styles.

For example, in the legal half-style: “to deal with a case” (case review); “summary procedure” (simplified procedure); “a body of judges” (panel of judges); “as laid down in” (as indicated); “the succeeding clauses of agreement” (subsequent paragraphs of the agreement); “to reaffirm faith in fundamental principles” (to reaffirm confidence in fundamental principles); “to establish the required conditions” (to set); “the obligations arising from treaties and other sources of international law” (obligations arising from treaties and other sources of international law), “the International Court of Justice” (international court); “casting vote” (decisive vote); “judicial authority”; “to hear a case” (hearing/hearing of the case), etc.

In the administrative half-style (in the financial sphere) we find such terms: “extra revenue (additional income); liability” (responsibility), “taxable capacities” (taxable cases); “liability to profit tax” (income tax liability), “profit” (income); “tax”; “currency”; “fee” (enrollment, registration, membership) - registration, membership payment; “banknotes”; “charge for” (to be a guarantor); “expenses”; “account”; “financial support”; “financial position” (situation) - financial condition; “cheque” etc.

Terms and expressions such as “high contracting parties” (“contracting parties);” to ratify an agreement (“ratification/ratification of an agreement);” memorandum;” pact “;” protectorate“;” extra-territorial status“;” plenipotentiary “ are typical of the diplomatic half-style [4, p.272].

As mentioned, an official-business stamp or template is a lexical-phraseological unit that helps to consider, that is, analyze situations or widespread concepts that are often repeated in a document. For example: during the report period (during the information period); solution of the problem (problem solving), maintain (in the sense of “repair”; instead of the word “repair”), to spoil (omit). These include words and phrases used in the official documents of the administrative half-style: appropriate, proper (necessary), foregoing (above-mentioned), undersigned (below-signed), non-execution, forward (sending), petitioner (applicant), guarantor, to assure possession of equal rights (providing equal rights). When using terms in business documentation, it is necessary to monitor the correct understanding of the term by both the author and the addressee. If the author of an official document, for

example, a letter, has doubts about this, it is necessary to disclose the content of the term in several ways: to give a formal definition of the term; to remove the term and replace it with words of a general, neutral lexicon.

The lack of consensus in the understanding of words can lead not only to the disruption of the communication process, but also to the bankruptcy of the firm. The high limit of unification (i.e. standard) is the use of terms. The official-business style of the English language-many works are devoted to the use of terms in it [3, p.332].

The following words and expressions can be attributed to the terminology of the official-business style:

1) Official-job titles of persons for their duties in business relations: plaintiff, pretender; defender; lodger, tenant; paying taxes (person); depositor; leaseholder; consumer; contractor; (person) shown above; (person) putting signature below; recipient; adopter; witness; declarant.

2) names of documents: order, direction, bidden; report, record of proceedings; proceedings, protocol, etc.

3) the names of the important components of the document, for example, the sender and recipient, and their legal addresses: the Buyer, the Lender, the Owner; the name of various operations: diary task; with the participation of smb.; smb. are presence; as mentioned above, the use of nominative lexical units is typical for this style, which most likely tell about the communicative conditions that will be used. For example, the presence of the following words allows us to say that the text is related to banking activities: to endorse – to make a pass note in someone else's name or put a signature on the back of the check; a now-account is a type of bank account in which the bank does not make payments on single checks

4) the use of common words and expressions in a special sense: picking out (easy earnings obtained by petty theft), forcing (forcing), squandering (uneconomical, reckless spending), commit (committing a crime), finding (court order), beer diplomacy; bread-and-butter letter (compound word or holophrasis phrases), black tie, lame duck, bench etc.;

5) abbreviated words: RPT – repeat; OK – consent.

6) graphic abbreviations: Mr, Mrs, Ms, Miss, Sir.

Unlike scientific terminology, the terminology of the official-business style is less abstract. The use of terms is conditioned by the content of official documents. Terms related to legal, diplomatic and accounting are among the most used: deed (act), levy (collection, accumulation), legalization (legislation), defender (defendant, trustee), to confirm, declarant, etc. [7, p.19].

Some nouns formed from the verb do not have a common term when they act as terms: inquiry (questioning), punishment (punishing), misprision of felony (not reporting: about a crime), picking out (easy profit obtained by petty theft), alienation (distancing, coldness), squandering (uneconomical, reckless spending), commit (committing a crime), finding (court order), stealing (hijacking a car).

In comparison with the verb, the use of nouns formed from the verb is more typical for the official-business style: put additives instead of the word add, a give a commission instead of the word entrust, a bring the responsibility instead of the word respond, a make a decision instead of the word decides, a bring amplifications instead of the, word amplify, make payment instead of the word respond pay.

In the official-business style, relative and complete synonyms can be noted. Full synonyms differ in their origin: original and derived synonyms. For example, "legislation" and "parliament" (both terms denote the place of adoption of the law); in the legal terminology: border–frontier (border); individual – person (personality); to own – to possession; "paternity" – "fatherhood"; "doles mauls" – "malice"; "delict – cake"; "place of residence" – "habitat"; "crime" – "offense".

The meaning core of relative synonyms is the same, and the components of the remaining periphery meanings are different. For example: deposit (deposit in the bank) and investment (capital investment); catastrophe (disaster) – accident; crash (car accident) – wreck (accident on the railway and in sea); clients (customers) – customers (buyers); reason (cause, basis) – motive (basis, inclination, etc.).

In the literary language, although synonyms mean a common or close meaning, in certain half-style of the official-business style, these words are used as separate terms. For example, the words larceny and theft denote different criminal names in criminal law: larceny means theft; theft means caprice, robbery. Embezzlement "wastefulness"; the term squandering more accurately denotes a type of war crime, which is "uneconomical, reckless spending", compared to its terms, which mean shortage "lack". Or the following concept synonyms are used as separate terms in criminal law: executor, organizer, abettor (accomplice), instigator; responsibility, responsiveness; punishment – reproach [14, p.136].

Official-business style words also form an antonymic row: plaintiff – defender "plaintiff - defendant", democracy – dictatorship "democracy – dictatorship", punished – acquired "punished - justified", aggravating – extenuating (circumstances) "aggravating – mitigating (reasons)", etc. As we can see, the terms that form antonyms are formally lexical antonyms, that is, these terms are more aimed at reflecting the positive aspect of the concept: punished – acquired "punished - justified", "aggravating – mitigating (reasons)", plaintiff – defender "plaintiff - defendant (defendant)", democracy – dictatorship "democracy – dictatorship", not only expressing the negation of contradiction: (grammatical/verbatim antonyms): guilt – guiltlessness "guilt, guilt – innocence, impudence".

Therefore, there are antonyms with both the same and different roots: "to appoint" – "to disappoint"; "juridical person" – "physical person"; "active" – "inactive"; "legal" – "illegal", "guilty" – "innocent", "justice" – "injustice", "rightful" – "unrightfully", "merciless" – "merciful", "punish ability" – "unpunish ability", "sanctioned" – "unsanctioned" [1,p.121]

For a long time, there has been an opinion in stylistics that emotionality is not expressed in the official-business style, and in fact, the emotional function of

words is lost: to have the honour, to be pleased, yours sincerely, etc. As we have noted, documents drawn up in this style already contain clichés, and the writer must necessarily follow these rules: we beg to inform you, on behalf of, provided that, with a view to, to expire, etc. For example, gives such a classic example of a letter for the middle of the 20th century:

"Dear Sir,

We recently had the honour of sending you a catalogue of steel shelving units and trust that you duly received the same.

As we have not yet been favoured with your order, we venture to enquire, if you have reached a decision, and should this not be the case, whether you require further information about our lock shelf system.

We await your esteemed instructions, which shall have our careful attention.

Your faithfully"

The underlined text is now archaic and unacceptable. In modern times, personal style, naturalness, and simplicity of expression come to the fore in official letters. In order to get a positive response, they have often begun to use impressive, persuasive means in official letters.

"Dear Mr. Morton,

You wish to modernize your stock and store rooms with most up-to-date shelving system yet devised. That is clear because you asked for a catalogue, which was sent to you earlier in the month.

The next step, lies, of course, with you. You could have a demonstration of the fitting of the "lock shelf" system in your own showrooms.

You could test for yourself the wonderful adaptability of our system to all storage problems, by sending us a trial order for one 15-ft section, which comprises three units or if you have some special problems, you are welcome to our advice without any obligation.

You may be sure that whichever of our services you decide to use, you will receive our immediate and personal attention.

Yours faithfully" [1, p. 122].

However, we consider a letter written in such a style unacceptable, because here, noted [4, p. 273], the addressee wrote the agreement not from his own personal point of view, but from the point of view of the recipient. Such a "compliment" is unacceptable. This style is called the "you-attitude" and is characteristic of American correspondence, which is more focused on practical goals.

In the diplomatic sub-style, pompous and bookish words are often used: guest of honor, courtesy visit, accompanied persons, entourage, etc. In the etiquette lexicon, sometimes historicisms are also found: *His Majesty, His highness, His Excellency, Lady, Gentleman, mistress, master, witness, the assurances of reverence, the above-mentioned*, etc.; and official formulas expressing diplomatic politeness are also included: *present compliments to; in deepest respect, feel much obliged; beg to thank, etc.*

The diplomatic sub-style is also characterized by an emotional-expressive tone: with *great interest* to consider the issues, *deeply concerned; strongly appealing* ... This feature brings it closer to the journalistic style.

Here we should note that the terms used in criminal law, although they directly indicate an assessment, are non-expressive, because these terms, first of all, express a legal assessment: active participation in group actions, harmful consequences, bad treatment to prisoners of war, gentle punishment, extremely dangerous recidivist, hooligan consequences, etc.

Along with this, expressive vocabulary is also used, which indicates the formality of the text or a negative, unpleasant attitude towards certain events: retribution, laying, encroachment, concealment, instigations, abettors, carelessness.

M.M. Mustfayeva divides diplomatic lexicon into two large groups: terms and professional words. Terms include words and word combinations related to international law and international relations; international abbreviations are noted. Professional words include words and word combinations, professional words and word combinations with a narrow meaning, and abbreviations used only in this field [16, p.174]. Let's look at the following terms.

“Diplomacy – noun. 1. The activity of managing relations between different countries; the skill in doing this: international diplomacy; diplomacy is better than war.

2. Skill in dealing with people in difficult situations without upsetting or offending them. Syn. Tact. See also shuttle diplomacy». «Shuttle diplomacy – noun. International talks in which people travel between two or more countries in order to talk to the different governments involved” [11, p.25].

“Diplomat – noun. 1 (also old-fashioned diplomatist) a person whose job is to represent his or her country in a foreign country, for example, in an embassy. 2. A person who is skilled at dealing with other people” [11, p.25]. The word “diplomat” means an employee of a foreign affairs agency that carries out official relations with other countries. In most cases, this word refers to an employee who holds a certain staff position in the central apparatus of a foreign policy department, or acts as a member of the staff of one of the foreign relations bodies - an embassy, country's representations in international intergovernmental organizations. This word was first used in 1681 by the Frenchman J. Mobilion in the book “De re diplomatic a”, and then passed into other languages M.M. Mustafayeva, analyzing the word "diplomat", shows that this noun passed from French to other languages through direct borrowing. The meaning of the word did not change during the borrowing process [11, p.25].

Letters of recall - a document about the recall of a diplomatic representative from his post. It is sent by the head of state who appointed the diplomatic representative to the head of state to which he is accredited. It came into English through the French language (*lettres de rappel*) and has not undergone any change in meaning.

The word "letter" also creates an idiomatic expression: *The letter of the law (often disapproving) the exact words of a law or rule rather than its general meaning: They insist on sticking to the letter of the law. To the letter – doing /following exactly what sb/sth says, paying attention to every detail: I followed your instructions to the letter” [11, p.25].*

Credentials – “1. – (as/for sth.) the qualities, training or experience that make you suitable to do sth.: He has all the credentials for the job. She will first have to establish her leadership credentials. 2. Documents such as letters that prove that you are who you claim to be, and can therefore be trusted” [11, p.25].

Warrant of attorney – this word denotes a document that helps to carry out the accreditation of a diplomatic mission, confirms the identity of the diplomatic representative and the diplomatic purpose of the mission. This document, which is for ambassadors and envoys, is drawn up in the manner accepted from one head of state to another and is certified by the appropriate signature and seal. The signature of the head of state is usually confirmed by the head of the foreign affairs department. During accreditation, chargé d'affaires and political representatives are provided with a letter from the foreign affairs department of the sending state to the foreign affairs department of the receiving state.

Analysis of the word shows that this word first appeared in French as “lettres de creance”. Later, this word combination passed into English in the variant credential- credentials. Although the word “Credentials” differs structurally, it retains the original semantics.

“Diplomatic protocol – 1. A system of fixed rules and formal behavior used at official meetings, usually between governments: a breach of protocol; the protocol of diplomatic visits. 2. The first or original version of an agreement, especially a treaty between countries, etc.; an extra part added to an agreement or treaty: the first Geneva Protocol. It is set out in a legally binding protocol which forms part of the treaty”.

“This expression is the generally accepted rules, traditions, and conditions taken into account by governments, foreign affairs departments, diplomatic missions, employees, and other officials in international relations” [8, p.23]. The word protocol is derived from the Greek word *protokolla* (*protos* – first, *kolla* – to glue).

In the Middle Ages, this expression reflected the meaning of preparing documents and creating archives. Later, this expression was associated with the field of diplomacy. Along with the rules for preparing diplomatic documents, diplomatic protocol includes etiquette and ceremonial rules. As a diplomatic term, it was first used in French at the end of the 17th century. Later, it passed into English and retained its meaning and form: Fr. *protocole* – Eng. *protocol*.

Diplomatic visit – a diplomatic visit – “is a means of establishing, maintaining and developing relations with representatives of the official, public and business circles of the country where diplomats are located, as well as with the diplomatic corps. Official diplomatic visits considered necessary include visits before and after the presentation of credentials by a diplomatic representative” [8, p.23].

The term diplomatic visit is of French origin. Like the term diplomatic corps, the expression diplomatic visit has also been borrowed, retaining the original meaning, but with a change in structure: in French, this term is formed with the noun+adj (*visite diplomatique*) model, and in English, on the contrary, with the

adj+noun (diplomatic visit) model. This is related to the syntactic structure of these languages.

Diplomatic mission, diplomatic representation, diplomatic correspondence, diplomatic mail, diplomatic courier, diplomatic note - these terms are of French origin. "*Diplomatic immunity* - noun. *Special rights given to diplomats working in a foreign country which means they cannot be arrested, taxed, etc. in that country*". "*The diplomatic service* - noun. *The government department concerned with representing a country in foreign countries*" [11, p.25].

Courier's papers, gentlemen's agreement are English terms, formed with the noun+noun model. *Persona grata/non grata* is a loanword from French, formed with the *noun+noun* model. Generalizing the features of official documents, it distinguishes morphological, syntactic, lexical and compositional features separately. For example, it is noted as a morphological feature that, according to the norm, legislative documents sometimes use outdated and even archaic means [5, p.380].

Linguistic features of the official business style.

1. At the level of vocabulary and phraseology: Official vocabulary, the main stylistic means of the official business style, for example: the ambassador presents (not transfers) credentials linguistic features of the official business style at the level of vocabulary and phraseology: Official vocabulary, the main stylistic means of the official business style, for example: the ambassador presents (not transfers) credentials.

2. Special words and terms, the appearance of which is due to the content of the document: legal (defendant, plaintiff, penalty, legislation), diplomatic (powers of attorney, ambassador extraordinary, convention), military (fortifications, missile launcher, defensive fortifications), economic (claim, tax collection, cassation appeal), etc.

3. Names of administrative bodies, structural divisions of organizations: Main Administration, Educational and Methodological Commission, Faculty Council, etc.

4. Names of persons by position (director, manager, chief agronomist) and by profession (teacher, educator, crane operator, driver) [17, 84].

Generalizing the features of official documents, it distinguishes morphological, syntactic, lexical and compositional features separately. For example, it is noted as a morphological feature that, according to the norm, legislative documents sometimes use outdated and even archaic means [1, p.121].

As a result of the development of the vocabulary of the English language, unique rules have emerged regarding the word formation of modern English.

These rules used in the word formation of the English language have been created and enriched entirely on the basis of the historical development of this language and its grammatical structure. New words that are created based on the rules of word formation of the English language mainly occur in the following three processes:

1) the process of lexical formation of new word units (here we can note the growth of words due to loanwords, semantic change, conversion and simplification of words);

2) the process of morphological formation of new words (through affixes);

3) the process of syntactical formation of new words (the formation of compound words and the method of abbreviation).

As we can see, this classification is somewhat different: morphological and syntactic methods are combined; it is not indicated to which method the simplification process belongs. In addition, borrowings are also noted in the formation of complex words. This is explained by the fact that the more important the concept expressed by borrowings, the higher their frequency of use in complex structures will be.

As a result of the process of developing the vocabulary of the English language, peculiar rules have been formed that relate to the word formation of the modern English language. These rules, which are used in the word creation of the English language, arose and enriched entirely on the basis of the ways of historical development and grammatical structure of this language. New words of the English language, formed on the basis of the rules of Word formation, occur mainly in the following three processes:

1) the process of lexical formation of new word units (here we can note the increase in words due to the acquisition of words, semantic change, conversion and simplification of words);

2) the process of morphological formation of new words (through suffixes);

3) the process of formation of new words by syntactic way (method of formation and abbreviation of complex words).

The new lexicon of the official-business style of the English language is formed by various methods: lexical, morphological, syntactic. In the lexical method of word creation, conversion, special verbalization, is distinguished by high productivity. The lexical-semantic method is also manifested in the narrowing and expansion of the main meaning in words. A number of military terms have gone from administrative to sub-administrative, for example, to business (strategy, action, operations, campaign, force (sales force, task force), division, chief, officer, target, conflict, defeat, capture, strengths, threats, resources, (economic) blockade). Since legal, diplomatic and semi-classes are more subject to social changes, the processing of a large number of acquisitions is monitored here. The new lexicon of the official-business style is also formed by suffixes (morphological method). By the syntactic method, complex words with different models are formed. Basically, nouns act as the main component of these models. Lexica's of the official-business style of the English language "Under the guise of syntactic means of various functional styles, it is necessary to understand the frequency of the use of one or another syntactic unit in various styles" [12, p. 18].

Studies show that, as a rule, the syntax of the official-business style is characterized by its complexity. We will reveal the syntactic features of the language of official-business documents in two aspects:

1) at the level of word combinations;

2) at the level of sentences and texts.

In repeated situations, a number of stereotyped word combinations and sentences are used: *herein after*

referred to as; to conclude the present contract to the following effect; referring to your telex; for further details;

We should divide official business of English its syntactic means into the following groups [14, p.136]:

1) attributive noun word combinations: verdict of guilty; court order, disciplinary prosecutions, verdict of "not guilty", preliminary investigation, the higher organs of power, fixed order. A two-part attributive noun that names different variants of a concept includes the word combination: for example, price types- landed price - the price of cargo unloading ashore (reduced price); list price- preyskurant price;

2) nominative groups that describe and define the concept expressed in the main word. For example: untimely notification – untimely notification of loading requisites; the timely execution of the obligations stipulated by the Contract - timely execution of obligations stipulated by the contract; tactical voting – “the act of voting for a particular person or political party, not because you support them, but in order to prevent sb. else from being elected” - tactical voting;

3) verb conjugations describing operations with the referent (expressed by the noun): to force down price-to lower the price; to rationalize price – to rationalize the price;

4) predicative and-hid, which streamline the actions of the parties and are used in an unknown kind. For example, facts ... shall be confirmed – facts must be confirmed; all disputes and differences ... are to be settled – all conflicts and differences...are justified.

5) multistage complex syntactic constructions (for example, some resolution texts). [17, p.84].

As we can see, there is not much difference between the first and second groups of syntactic units, while the fourth and fifth groups constitute a pure sentence.

Adherence to the norm eliminates different interpretations of the text and speeds up the communication process. Business standards are a means of expressing important stylistic and grammatical features of business English.

Two types of business standards can be distinguished: sentences and non-phraseological fixed word combinations. Business standards that act as sentences are distinguished within:

1) sentences that are frequently used in similar recurring situations and are semantically complete. Neither Party is entitled to transfer their rights or obligations under this contract to a third party without the other party's previous written comment.

2) constructions with units that change depending on specific situations: Goods shall be insured by ... with ... on condition. “The guarantee period is ... months from the date of ... but not more than ... months from the date of ...”

Non-phraseological fixed word combinations are divided into three groups:

1) word combinations prone to phraseologies, for example, dead freight; running hours - working hours; render assistance (used instead of the word "help"); to hold an inquiry into - to investigate; to make duties - to perform duties; to occupy a post - to hold a post; to lay an amenability - to lay an amenity on someone. The

meaning of the verbs listed does not coincide with the meaning of other synonymous verbs. For example, make a raid - an official terminological combination denoting a certain type of road accident, which means "to hit a car with a car".

2) word combinations used figuratively: dispatch money – (reward for quick unloading of cargo); commercial invoice – commercial payment; this line also includes a number of figurative stable word combinations related to the field of diplomacy: big stick diplomacy; cowboy diplomacy; cricket diplomacy; dollar diplomacy; gunboat diplomacy (“noun. A way of making another country accept your demands by using the threat of force”); mango diplomacy; panda diplomacy; ping-pong diplomacy; shuttle diplomacy; sports diplomacy; Track-II diplomacy; track-III diplomacy; smiles of diplomacy; short sleeve diplomacy.

3) synonymic substitution of the component, which does not lead to a change in the general meaning in stable word combinations: to put forward / to raise a claim – to put forward a claim; to lay claim to smth./ to put smth. in a claim - to present a right to a person/ make a claim (claim) to something. “In the legal field, the use of synonyms is conditioned in order to imply” all factors and circumstances " in life. However, in the legal field there are stabilized expressions in which complete synonymy is observed: to tell the truth, the whole truth and nothing but the truth. Null and void (without legal force)” [11, p. 25]. The fact that criminal law is a characteristic case of synonymous and synonymic constructions in the system of terms T. Uskova explains by the use of terms in various legal discourses [11, p. 7].

Thus, business standards in contracts perform a number of functions: eliminate ambiguity in the interpretation of events, realize the principle of economy in the language, create a certain stylistic effect – give the text a shade of decisiveness, formality, accuracy, non-emotionalit

Conclusion

We should note that the official-business style belongs to the type of style that performs the intellectual communicative function (termed: and that is, to the style of informing (the scientific style also belongs to the style that performs the intellectual communicative function). Other features that unite the official-business style and the scientific style are: accuracy and unambiguousness in the transmission of information; extensive use of clichés.

Thus, in the business style, it is appropriate to use certain formulas that bear the imprint of formality, specificity of means of expression, and speech standards.

The main features of the business style include clarity, precision, and detail in the presentation; clarity and strictness in the wording; logicity and conciseness in expressing thoughts; specific forms of arranging material, a certain "prescribed nature of speech"; standardization of speech patterns, stereo typicality, and uniformity of speech tools necessary for effective communication in this field. Expressions of objectivity, detail, and impersonality are important, as is the imperative and prescriptive nature of the presentation, with an impartial statement of facts and detailed categorization.

The goal is to achieve a common understanding, with a clear and unambiguous reading that does not allow for double interpretations, and to avoid repetition and unnecessary details.

The language of laws, "wrote L.V. Shcherba, "requires, first of all, precision and the impossibility of any misinterpretation. In this case, the speed of understanding is no longer extremely important, as an interested person will read every article of the law two or three times without any prompting."

References:

1. Alexander, L.G. Essay and letter writing. – London: Longman, – 1975.– 121p.
2. Crystal, D., Davys, D. Investigating English style. – London: Longman Group United Kingdom, – 1969. – 264 p.
3. Galperin, I.P. Stylistics. – Moscow: Higher school, – 1977. – 332 p.
4. Gowers, E. The Complete Plain Words. – London: Penguin Books, – 1968.– 272 p.
5. Partridge, E. Usage and Abusage. – London: Penguin ref. Books, – 1978.– 380p.
6. Swan, Michael. Practical English Usage. – Oxford, University Press, third edition, – 2008.– 658 p.
7. Дорошенко В.Ю. Коммуникативная обусловленность функционально-стилистических особенностей делового английского языка: //автореферат дисс. кандидата филологических наук. – Санкт-Петербург, – 1995.– 19с.
8. Колядин Е.А. Древнеанглийский законодательный свод как тип текста: // автореферат дисс. кандидата филологических наук. – Нижний Новгород, 2012.– 23с.
9. Маловичко М.Г. Становление и развитие функционального стиля официально-деловой документации в английском языке: прагматические, семантические, структурные аспекты: //Дисс. кандидата филологических наук. – С.-П., 2002.– 252с.
10. Путин А.А. О тропах устойчивых словесных комплексов английского языка древнего периода.– с.52-56// Структура лингвостилистики и ее основные категории. Межвуз. сб. науч. тр. – Пермь, – 1983.– 156с.
11. Ускова Т.В. Когнитивно-дискурсивные особенности англоязычной юридической терминологии: // Автореферат дисс. кандидата филологических наук. – Москва,– 2008.–25с.
12. Юсупова Т.С. Функционально-стилистические и прагматические характеристики англоязычного военного дискурса: // Автореферат дисс. кандидата филологических наук. / – Самара: Поволжский ун-т, 2010.– 18с.
13. Abdullayev S. Qeyri-səlis dilçilik təcrübəsi. – Bakı:Victory, – 2013.– 596s.
14. Ağakışiyeva Ş.M. Ədəbi dil normaları və üslublar: //filologiyəüzrəfəlsəfədoktoru dis. / – Bakı:AMEA, Dilçilik İnst-tu, 2008.– 136s.
15. Əfəndiyeva T. Azərbaycan ədəbi dilinin üslubiyat problemləri. – Bakı:Nurlan, 2007. 184s
16. Mustafayeva M.M. Azərbaycanda rəsmi-ışğuzar üslub və sənədləşmə tarixindən //Bakı Slavyan Universitetinin Elmi əsərləri. Dil və ədəbiyyat seriyası, – 2013. №1.– s.173-180.
17. Fataliyeva S.H. Stylistics of the English Language (Dərs vəsaiti). – Bakı:Mütərcim, – 2011.– 84s.